

SMILE PRESS RELEASE N° 2

**Supporting Mental health in young People:
Integrated Methodology for cLinical dEcisions and evidence-based interventions**

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Funded by the European Union under Grant Agreement No°101080923. Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

SMILE

Supporting Mental health in young People: Integrated Methodology for cLinical dEcisions and evidence-based interventions

The SMILE project, a collaborative effort by [15 Leading European Partners](#) who are actively working to empower the mental health of **young people aged from 10 to 24** and promote their wellbeing. Its goal is to prevent anxiety and depression by boosting resilience and offering accessible mental health support.

Innovative Digital Solutions for Youth

SMILE delivers personalised evidence-based interventions, raising awareness among parents, teachers, and mental health professionals. Since its launch, the SMILE project is making significant progress with its development of prototypes of the digital tools (gamification, Awareness APP and DSS), and the conduction of focus groups with young people ensuring that the SMILE solutions directly address their mental health challenges.

Help Shaping Solutions for Youth Mental Health!

The SMILE project seeks YOUR thoughts!

We're conducting a SHORT SURVEY to understand the biggest challenges young people face regarding mental health and wellbeing.

Your Voice matters! Take our [SHORT SURVEY NOW!](#)

Stay tuned for upcoming announcements about pilot programs and how you can get involved in supporting youth mental wellbeing!